

REINCARNATE

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Dear **changemaker**,

In our fifth issue, we are excited to share the latest updates on our project, which has received positive feedback from EU reviewers and is now at the **halfway point of its implementation**. This newsletter features numerous scientific publications available to researchers and industry professionals alike, contributed by both our **Tech4EUConstruction** cluster partners and our team.

Additionally, we delve into our vision for sustainability and inclusivity, presented through the lens of our multidisciplinary and international consortium.

We invite you to stay connected with us through our channels to keep abreast of all project activities.

Enjoy your reading!

HALFWAY OF OUR PROJECT, SO WHAT'S NEXT?

4th General Assembly

Meet the team members!

14-15 March

Valencia

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We are celebrating our **two-year anniversary** this month with positive feedback from the European Commission and a huge enthusiasm to continue our mission of transforming the built environment into a circular one. In this meeting, **the reviewers reminded us how each one of us plays an important role in accomplishing this mission.**

Our next steps are crucial as we prepare the innovative methods and technologies that will be demonstrated in real European construction assets. These advancements integrated into our **CPIM Reincarnate** include **Lean construction planning, Circular decision-making for extending the use life of real estate assets, Upgrade solutions for construction products, Valuation of recycled materials, and Adaptive refurbishment and renovation** of real estate assets, **Methods for BIM-supported dismantling, Parametric**

30 MUST-READ SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS BY THE TECH4EU CONSTRUCTION CLUSTER

30 MUST-READ SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

THE SCIENCE BEHIND CONSTRUCTION
GREEN AND SMART INNOVATIONS

humantech BEEYONDERS ROB@TARME

REINCARNATE InCUBE BIMTWIN Reconmatic HeroD

Together with the partners of the [Tech4EUConstruction](#) cluster we compiled **30 research publications in a blog article**. This joint work is a mine of information for researchers and industry professionals willing to explore the science behind next-generation technologies and innovations in areas such as building renovation, sustainability monitoring, digital innovation technologies, energy efficiency, renewable energy, and materials and design.

[Read it!](#)

SCIENCE AND RESEARCH BEHIND REINCARNATE'S INNOVATIONS

Reincarnate is going beyond theory

We release a pre-print [publication](#) exploring complex composition materials design through a comprehensive, comparative lab study of Data-Driven Design, using **SLAMD** (an open-source AI materials design tool) and traditional Design of Experiments (DOE).

[Discover more!](#)

How digital innovation is shaping a sustainable future in construction?

The [publication](#) highlights our aim to promote circular practices by extending material durability through digital methods, integrating NDT techniques and AI methods for material recycling.

[Explore the paper!](#)

An alkali-activated concrete dataset and its properties available

A recent [publication](#) explains the environmental benefits of substitution of traditional Portland concrete with alkali-activated concrete (AAC) mixes, and provides a ready-to-use [dataset](#) in various data-extensive research areas like machine learning and theoretical validation.

[Discover more!](#)

Outlining the criteria unfolding throughout each adaptive reuse decision-making process phase

One of our [publications](#) serves as the foundation for a circular decision-making framework for the **adaptive reuse** and renovation of real estate assets. This circular practice provides social, environmental, and economic benefits, including energy and material efficiency, safety, and better quality of living.

[Explore the paper!](#)

Find them all in this article by BUILD-UP EU

4 FRESH TECHNICAL DELIVERABLES

4 DELIVERABLES

Ontology, CP-IM Platform Launch Version,
Standardization and Impact Master Plan

Reincarnate has released the **first technical deliverables**, sharing openly the latest advancements in our project.

To address the lack of standardized terminology and concepts related to the circular economy in the built environment, we have developed "[An Ontology for circular management of buildings.](#)" The report provides a comprehensive language framework that facilitates a better understanding of key concepts and the implementation of circular economy practices.

Additionally, we have introduced the "[Launch Version of CPIMReincarnate](#)" deliverable, presenting the launch version of our platform designed to integrate green innovations within the built environment. This innovative platform features two main components: the open-source IoT platform Mainflux and the DMO RE Suite for real estate information.

Moreover, the "[Standardization Plan](#)" and "[Impact Master Plan](#)" reports are now found on our open access platform Zenodo, illustrating strategic guidance for our activities related to standardization, communication, dissemination, exploitation, and market uptake. These two deliverables are crucial for ensuring broad adoption and impact.

Read and download them!

REINCARNATE AROUND EUROPE

The team behind Reincarnate has actively participated in numerous onsite and online events across Europe. For the second consecutive year, we attended the [RILEM Convention in Milan](#), where we delivered 4 insightful presentations on our latest findings in circular economy and construction materials. Additionally, we took part in the [AMS Institute's scientific conference](#) in Amsterdam, titled "Reinventing the City: Blueprints for Messy Cities," where we shared our research on the circular adaptive reuse of buildings.

Returning to [OpenBIM Poland](#) for its second edition, we promoted our circular, social, and digital solutions. At the [Building Smart International Summit in Valencia](#), Spain —European Green Capital 2024—we engaged with stakeholders from the building smart ecosystem and gained enriching insights. Our learning journey continued at [IFAT Munich 2024](#), where we were inspired by the latest innovations in environmental technology and recycling.

Over the past months, we have forged significant alliances at clustering events aimed at promoting circularity in construction. Organised by our sister project RECONMATIC, a [webinar powered by EU-BUILD UP](#) gathered seven like-minded EU-funded projects advocating circular practices in the industry. Reincarnate is also progressing towards standardization, having engaged with the [Standardization Committee on Building Information Modelling \(BIM\)](#) and hosted internal [workshops](#) to align our partners. Furthermore, we held an internal workshop to discuss the [exploitation framework and methodology](#) that will be implemented throughout the project.

FRESH CAMPAIGNS

ROUNDTABLE DISCUSSION: SUSTAINABILITY AND INCLUSIVITY

#GirlsInICT #EarthDay

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In celebration of **Earth Day** and **Girls in ICT**, members of the team behind Reincarnate, from academia, construction companies, and NGOs, came together to share their perspectives on female representation in the digitisation of the circular construction industry. During a roundtable discussion, participants presented a range of initiatives, experiences, insights, and actions related to this important topic.

[Read the full article!](#)

Circular Alliances

CIRCULOOS

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Our mission is to expand our community of practice and connect with relevant networks through our **#CircularAlliances**. Recently, we established contact with the **CIRCULOOS project**, elevating sustainability trying the circular way of manufacturing. The exchange of our commonalities are gathered in an interview article, exploring the transformative opportunities they offer for micro, small and medium-sized enterprises towards circularity.

[Get to know them!](#)

UPCOMING OPPORTUNITIES

Reincarnate will be at the Sustainable Places Conference with the Tech4EUConstruction cluster

SUSTAINABLE PLACES 2024

From **September 23rd to 25th**, our construction cluster will convene at the **Sustainable Places Conference 2024** in Luxembourg. This conference will provide an enriching platform for the built environment sector, featuring research presentations, workshops, project clustering, and networking opportunities with stakeholders dedicated to promoting sustainability.

Interested stakeholders attending the conference are invited to join the two workshops organised by our cluster exploring the intersection of sustainable construction & renovation: **"Unlocking the Future: Exploring Digital Twins and Machine-Human Collaboration"** and **"Building the Future: Streamlining Innovative Materials for Sustainable Construction."**

[Learn more!](#)

BEYONDEERS: Human-centric innovation and

HumanTech: The brand new HumanTetch

RoBétArmé launched a new campaign, called 'RoBétArmé Research' !

skills for safety in construction

A recent **collaborative article** by EBC, Tecnia Research & Innovation, and Sci-track delves into the seamless integration of human-robot collaboration technologies to support workers and companies in addressing skill shortages in the European construction industry.

[Learn more!](#)

RESOURCES page is LIVE!

You can now explore its **#training** materials, **#OpenSource**, and **#deliverables** to learn more about the work they're doing to advance the digitalisation of the construction sector.

[Discover it!](#)

Throughout this **campaign**, we will hear from **PhDs, PostDocs, junior researchers, staff, master students, and interns** who are working on the RoBétArmé project. They will share their experiences regarding working on the project, how it aligns with their research, and how being part of a European-funded initiative can positively impact their careers.

[Find out more!](#)

Follow us and stay tuned!

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